

ROLE OF SIDDHA THERAPEUTICS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF NEURODEVELOPMENTAL DELAY SECONDARY TO REPAIRED ENCEPHALOCELE: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Encephalocele is a rare congenital neural tube defect characterized by herniation of intracranial contents through a cranial defect. Although early surgical correction improves survival, many children continue to experience long-term neurological sequelae, including global developmental delay and motor impairment. In Siddha medicine, such pediatric neuromuscular dysfunctions are correlated with derangement of *Vatham* and are described under *Balar Vatham*. A 5-year-old female child with a history of surgically repaired encephalocele and unilateral right ventriculoperitoneal shunt placement on the fourth day of life presented with unable to walk independently without support. Although the child was able to speak clearly and communicate her needs, gross motor development was significantly delayed, and Neurological examination revealed mild motor weakness in the lower limb. The child was treated

with a *Siddha* therapeutic regimen consisting of internal medicines such as *Dharany Brahme* Syrup, *Ashwagandhathi Chooranam*, and *Deshanthun Kalka*, along with external therapies including body massage with *Nirgundiathi oil* and *Maha Narayana oil* and herbal bath. The treatment aimed to pacify the deranged *Vatham*, enhance neuromuscular strength, and improve functional mobility. Following treatment, gradual improvement in lower limb strength, coordination, and balance was observed. Most notably, the child achieved independent walking without support, which had not been accomplished prior to treatment. This case highlights the potential role of *Siddha* therapeutic management in facilitating motor

milestone attainment in children with developmental delay secondary to repaired Encephalocele. Structured *Vatha*-pacifying and neuromuscular-strengthening interventions may contribute for functional improvement, warranting further systematic clinical evaluation.

KEYWORDS: Developmental delay, Encephalocele, *Siddha* medicine, *Balar Vatham*, Pediatric neurology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human development refers to the physical, cognitive, and psychosocial changes that occur throughout the lifespan, and these lines of progress develop sequentially and independently over time. The development of the fetal brain starts during the first trimester, more specifically in the fourth week of gestation, and continues throughout pregnancy with very rapid growth in early childhood but continuing actively through adolescence and into the middle of the third decade of life with ongoing development throughout the lifespan (Khan I et al. 2023).

Global estimates show that 52.9 million children under 5 years old have developmental disabilities and 95% of them live in low and middle-income countries. Without appropriate support and a facilitative environment, these conditions often limit the ability of children with developmental delays to benefit from the opportunities provided (WHO, 2023).

Developmental delay in a child occurs when the child fails to achieve any one aspect of development; gross motor, fine motor, speech, and social development by an appropriate age and it is influenced by a range of factors such as socio-economic, biological, maternal, environmental, nutritional and genetic factors (Bishwokarma A, et al. 2022). Delay in development is generally determined when a child does not attain developmental milestones as compared to peers from the same population.

Congenital neural tube defects, such as encephalocele refers to the herniation of intracranial contents through the defect in the dura and calvarium. Encephalocele is a rare entity in routine radiology practice; hence, a radiologist challenged with a case of cephalocele may find oneself lacking appropriate knowledge and reporting skills required to provide an optimal report (Pal et al. 2021).

The most common anatomical location of encephaloceles varies by geographic distribution, with occipital encephaloceles most common in Europe and North America, and

frontoethmoidal encephaloceles most common in Russia and Southeast Asia. The most common encephaloceles occur on a sporadic basis and are not associated with syndromes. Embryology is complex and may vary by location. (Micael C & Brodsky. 2010).

With encephalocele, a baby is born with a sac-like protrusion of brain tissue coming out of an opening in the skull. The opening can be anywhere along the center of the skull, from the nose to the back of the neck. The most common locations are the back of the head, the top of the head, or between the forehead and the nose. An encephalocele at the back of the skull is more likely to cause nervous system problems. Encephalocele can also lead to other issues such as: Buildup of excess fluid in the brain, Complete loss of strength in the arms and legs, Developmental delay or intellectual disability, vision problems,, and Seizures (CDC, 2026).

Signs of encephalocele can include: too much fluid in the brain, loss of strength in the arms and legs, a small head, awkward movement of muscles such as those used in walking and reaching, delay in growth and development, problems seeing, problems with breathing, heart rate, and swallowing, and seizures. Different types of encephalocele include; Meningocele: This type of encephalocele usually does not cause any major problems. The bulge through the skull is filled with spinal fluid. encephalocele: This is a serious condition that can cause long-term neurological (brain) problems. The sac-like bulge that pokes through the opening in the skull contains brain tissue and spinal fluid. The brain tissue in the sac is not normal. The rest of the brain may also be affected.

Encephalocele is usually found during a perinatal ultrasound. Fetal MRI is a non-invasive imaging test to get a clearer, more detailed image of your baby's organs, especially the brain. A fetal echocardiogram is a specialized ultrasound used to examine the heart and blood vessels around it. Other genetic tests include cell-free fetal DNA testing, Amniocentesis, and testing the baby after birth using a blood sample to look for chromosome problems.

Several genetic syndromes are associated with encephalocele. Medical problems with the mother, such as diabetes, have been connected with the development of encephalocele. There is some proof that being exposed to toxic chemicals, including certain medicines, could increase the risk of having a baby with encephalocele. However, no one knows what causes encephalocele.

Encephalocele is a congenital condition belonging to a group of nervous system disorders known as neural tube defects. Adequate intake of folic acid (Vitamin B9) before conception

and during early pregnancy significantly reduces the risk of neural tube defects. Folic acid is naturally present in leafy green vegetables, nuts, beans and citrus fruits and is also added to fortified foods such as breakfast cereals. In addition, prenatal vitamin supplements provide an important source of folic acid to support healthy fetal development (Nationwide children's Hospital. 2026).

Although early surgical repair improves survival, many children continue to experience long-term neurological deficits. Integrative medicine, which combines conventional medical care with evidence informed traditional therapies, has gained attention as a supportive strategy for improving functional outcomes and quality of life in chronic neurological conditions. This case report describes the integrative management of developmental delay in a child with repaired encephalomyelocele.

“*Balar Vatham*” refers to *Vatha rogam* occurring in the pediatric age group. In Siddha medicine, body movements and physical activities such as sitting, walking, running, lying down, and speaking are governed by *Vatham*. When there is a derangement of *Vatham*, these functional activities may be impaired.

Children who experience difficulty or inability in performing age-appropriate motor and physical functions due to vitiation of *Vatham* are categorized under “*Balar Vatham*.” This condition presents with varying degrees of functional disability depending on the severity and nature of the *Vatha* imbalance.

Cause of *Balar Vatham*

“*Solliya balavatham thodaranthidum viparamkel*

Melliya karuvil vanthu meviya thisai vayukkal

Nalliyalillamal than nathamum serumakil

Thalliya kunamum vidduthanthidum naramputhane”

Balavatha nithanam

The origin of *Balar Vatham* is attributed to the derangement of *Thasa Vayukkal* during the period of conception. This disturbance may lead to abnormalities in the fertilized ovum and subsequently interfere with normal fetal development, resulting in neurological disability in the child (Sivathanupillai, 2001)

Sign and symptoms of *Balar vatham*.

*“Valaiyenra kuzhanthaiku vatham vanthal
Vasamkeddu kaikalum vilankidathu
Kolalemenra sakthiyathu kurainthu kanum
Kulainthu vilum narampellam thalarntu nitkum
Kalamenra kal karamum yidda polam
Kandaththil visai thalarum kaluththu konum
Seelamika Nadakka Odda Seetham Thonrum
Thekaththil kulirsaiyundam viraiikkum thane.”*

Mathalainoi thokuthi

The signs and symptoms of *Balar Vatham*, as described in the classical stanza, include inability to use the limbs, reduced muscular strength, reduced muscle tone, and chillness and numbness in the affected limbs (Mohanraj, 2009).

2. METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This study is a descriptive observational case report of a paediatric patient who developed developmental delays following surgical repair of encephalocele. The case was selected due to its clinical significance and the long-term neurodevelopmental implications associated with neural tube defects.

Patient Selection

The case was identified during in the paediatric outpatient clinic. Inclusion was based on documented history of encephalocele repair and subsequent evidence of developmental delay during follow-up assessments.

Data Collection

Clinical data were collected retrospectively and prospectively from:

- Hospital medical records
- Surgical notes
- Neonatal intensive care records
- Follow-up clinic visits
- Developmental assessment reports
- Mother statement

Diagnostic and Developmental Assessment

- Neurological examination
- Developmental screening using standardized paediatric developmental assessment tools
- Hearing and vision assessment
- Anthropometry assessment

Developmental delay was assessed across major domains:

- Gross motor
- Fine motor
- Speech and language
- Social and adaptive behaviour

Therapeutic Interventions

Following identification of developmental delay, the patient was treated with internal medicines and external therapy

Progress was monitored during scheduled follow-up visits over a defined period.

Ethical Considerations

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's mother parent/guardian prior to documentation and publication of this case.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 5-year-old female child was brought in with complaints of inability to walk without assistance since birth. She was diagnosed with encephalomyelocele at birth and underwent surgical excision on the fourth day of life. A right-sided ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt was also placed on the same day. According to the mother statement, the child failed to achieve age-appropriate developmental milestones, with delays observed in all domains. Independent walking has not achieved yet. At four years of age, the child experienced a single episode of partial tonic-clonic seizure affecting the left upper and lower limbs, lasting approximately ten minutes, with no history of recurrence. At the time of presentation, the child was able to sit independently, hold her neck, respond to auditory and visual stimuli, and communicate basic needs such as hunger and urination. There was no history of fever, drooling, difficulty swallowing, bowel or bladder incontinence, or behavioral disturbances. The antenatal history revealed that the mother was unaware of her pregnancy until five months gestation and therefore, had not consumed folic acid during the early pregnancy.

Clinical findings

On examination, the child was conscious, cooperative, and lean-built. Vital signs were stable. There was no pallor, icterus, cyanosis, clubbing, or lymphadenopathy. Ankle joint abnormality was noted.

Neurological examination revealed normal muscle tone and bulk in all limbs, with muscle power graded as 4/5 in both upper and lower limbs. Deep tendon reflexes were normal at the knee and ankle joints, while plantar reflexes were diminished. Sensory responses to touch, pain, and temperature were intact. Assessment revealed deficits in Higher cortical functions. Cardiovascular, respiratory, and gastrointestinal system examinations were normal.

Based on Siddha diagnostic stool in three Humors *Viyanan*, *Samanan*, *Nagan*, *Sathaka Piththam*, and *Santhika kabam* were affected. In *Saptha Thathukkal Oon* and *Enbu* were affected and *Kaba Vatha Naadi* was noted.

Diagnostic assessment

Based on clinical history and examination, the child was diagnosed with global developmental delay secondary to congenital Encephalomyelocele, status postsurgical repair and ventriculoperitoneal shunt placement. The condition was considered as neurodevelopmental in origin.

Therapeutic intervention

The *Siddha* therapeutic approach was adopted, combining conventional medical monitoring with traditional therapeutic interventions aimed at neuromuscular stimulation, cognitive support, and overall functional improvement.

Internal medicines

Darany syrup: 5ml twice daily after food

Ashwagandha choornam: 0.5g twice daily after food

Deshanthun Kalka: 0.5g twice daily after food

Which are the herbal formulations with neuroprotective, adaptogenic, and strength-promoting properties. Medications were administered in age-appropriate doses under clinical supervision.

External therapies

Head and Body massage with *Nirgundiya* oil for first 7 days then *Maha Narayana* oil for another 7 days.

Herbal bath after oil application of whole body with *Nirgundiya* oil in once a week.

These manual therapy techniques are applied to the back and lower limbs to enhance neuromuscular activation. The oil-based therapies and herbal applications support sensory integration and motor coordination. The head application and body stimulation procedures are administered for a fixed duration.

1. *Desanthun Kalka*

Ingredients

Horse gram	<i>Macrotyloma uniflorum</i> (Lam) Verdc
Red sandalwood	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> Linn
White sandal wood	<i>Santalum alba</i> Linn.f
Sweet flag	<i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn
Liquorice	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> Linn
Pink rock salt	<i>Sodium chloride</i>

Desanthun Kalka is traditionally indicated in pediatric conditions such as convulsions, fever, and certain skin disorders but empirically it uses for enhance the immune system. It can be administered in a dosage ranging from 125 mg to 250 mg, depending on the age, body weight, and clinical condition of the child (Department of Ayurveda, 1975)

2. *Ashwaganthathi chooranam*

Ingredients

Winter cherry	<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L) Dunal
Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe
Long pepper	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn
Black pepper	<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn
Trumpet	<i>Stereospermum colais</i>
Curry leave	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> L. Spreng
Spikenard	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> (D.Don) DC
Galangal	<i>Alpinia galanga</i> (L) willd
Kutki	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i> Royle ex Benth

Ashwagandha Chooranam is indicated in the management of *Vatha* disorders and generalized body weakness. It is usually administered in a dose ranging from half to two tea spoon full, as directed by the physician, depending on the patient's age, condition, and clinical requirements (Department of Ayurveda, 1975)

3. Dharany Brahmee (Lunuwila) Syrup

Ingredients

Brahmi	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L)
Black seed	<i>Nigella sativa</i> Linn
Giloy	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd)
Mountain knotgrass	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L) Juss ex Schult
Honey and Sugar	

Dharany Syrup is specially recommended for memory enhancement and cognitive support. It also helps protect the vocal cords, improve eyesight, and provide therapeutic benefits for certain skin disorders, epilepsy, and mental health conditions. For children aged 6–12 years, it is administered in a dose ranging from half to one teaspoonful, as prescribed by the physician (Department of Ayurveda, 1975).

4. Nirgundiathi oil

Ingredients

Chinese caste tree	<i>Vetex negundo</i> L
Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe
Cardamom	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> L
Cinnamon	<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i> Blume
Black pepper	<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn
Long pepper	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn
Black seed	<i>Nigella sativa</i> Linn
Gingelly oil	

Nirgundiathi oil is indicated for diseases of the head, rhinitis, and tinnitus. It is beneficial in relieving nasal congestion, sinus-related discomfort, and ear-related symptoms associated with *Vatha–Kapha* imbalance (Department of Ayurveda, 1975).

Bael	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> Linn (Bael)
Winter cherry	<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L) Dunal
Horse purslane	<i>Trianthema decandra</i> Linn
Egg plant	<i>Solanum melongena</i> var <i>insanum</i> L
Flannel weed	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L
Wild asparagus	<i>Asperagus racemosus</i> (Wild)
Indian madder	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i> Linn
Himalayan cedar	<i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb) LOUD
Wild ginger	<i>Costus speciosus</i> (Koeing sm)
Pelitory	<i>Anacyclus pyrenthem</i> DC
Spikenard	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> (D.Don) DC
Gypsum	<i>Calcium sulfatate dehydrate</i>
Gingelly oil	

Maha Narayana oil is indicated in conditions such as hemiplegia, Bell's palsy, and muscle wasting. It is traditionally used to alleviate *Vatha* disorders, improve muscle tone, and enhance neuromuscular function (Department of Ayurveda, 1975).

DISCUSSION

Siddha Therapeutic Correlation of Medicinal Ingredients

In *Siddha* medicine, neurological dysfunctions, including delayed motor and cognitive development, are often correlated to disturbances in *Vatham*, especially in conditions that involve compromised neuromuscular coordination and cognitive delay. *Withania somnifera*, used in *Ashwagandha Chooranam*, is described in traditional texts as a potent *Vatha* pacifier and *Rasayana* (rejuvenator) with the ability to strengthen muscles and nervous tissue. Modern pharmacological studies support its neuroprotective, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and adaptogenic properties, which contribute to neuronal viability and synaptic plasticity, mechanisms important in neurodevelopmental progression (Singh et al., 2011; Tandon & Yadav, 2020). Withanolides from *W. somnifera* have been shown to stimulate neurite outgrowth and modulate neurotransmitter activity, which may help improve muscle strength and cognitive responsiveness in children with brain insults.

Zingiber officinale, another ingredient in the formulation, is traditionally used to improve circulation and reduce *Ama*, which, in *Siddha* logic, contributes to the blockage of *srotas* (channels) and impairs neuromuscular functions. Its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects are supported by experimental evidence showing reduced levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines in neural tissues and improved cerebral circulation (Mashhadi et al., 2013). Such actions may help reduce neuroinflammation and support synaptic efficiency in developmental disorders.

Piper species - *Piper longum* and *Piper nigrum* - are described in *Siddha* texts as Bio-enhancers and *Vatham* stabilizers when used with other medicines. Modern studies confirm that piperine enhances the bioavailability of active phytochemicals and exerts neuroprotective and neuromodulatory effects through modulation of neurotransmitter systems (Prasad et al., 2014). These effects may support neurotransmitter balance and neuromuscular responsiveness.

Nardostachys jatamansi, historically indicated in *Siddha* medicine for neurological derangements including convulsive conditions, contains bioactive sesquiterpenes with

documented anticonvulsant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective actions (Bhatt et al., 2012). Given the history of seizure in the present case, its ability to protect neurons from excitotoxicity and oxidative stress may support neural stability and maturation.

Picrorhiza kurroa is traditionally used for its *deepana* and *pittahara* effects, which, in Siddha logic, help clear *Ama* and balance biological fire, indirectly supporting nervous system health. Phytochemical studies demonstrate its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities (Raina et al., 2002), which may help reduce neuroinflammation associated with developmental delay.

Bacopa monnieri, a principal herb in *Dharany Brahme* Syrup, is classically indicated as *Medhya Rasayana* to enhance cognitive functions. Modern research supports its role in promoting dendritic proliferation, enhancing cholinergic transmission, and protecting against oxidative neuronal damage (Stough et al., 2001; Aguiar & Borowski, 2013). In children with delayed speech and cognitive function, these actions can support attention, memory, and overall neurodevelopment.

Nigella sativa is included for its balancing effects on *Vatham* and *Pitham* and is described in traditional texts to support neurological health. Contemporary studies show that thymoquinone from *N. sativa* exerts antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects in neural tissue and may improve learning and memory performance (Ahmad et al., 2013). This aligns with the observed improvements in attention and responsiveness.

Tinospora cordifolia, another ingredient of *Dharany Brahme* Syrup, is traditionally considered a strong *Vatham* and *Kapha* balancer with *Rasayana* properties that nourish the nervous system. Pharmacological studies demonstrate immunomodulatory and neuroprotective effects that may reduce the levels of inflammatory mediators contributing to neuronal dysfunction (Singh et al., 2020).

Acorus calamus in *Deshanthun Kalka* is traditionally used in pediatric neurological disorders for *pacification of Medhya and Vatham*. Its actions include enhancement of cerebral circulation and modulation of neurotransmitter systems, which have been supported by experimental evidence for improved cognitive performance (Mukherjee et al., 2007). In this case, it may have contributed to improved speech responsiveness and higher mental functions.

Glycyrrhiza glabra is added for its *Pithahara* and *Rasayana* effects, which help mitigate inflammation and support modulation of the HPA axis. Modern studies demonstrate its neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory properties (Boskabady et al., 2011), which may help stabilize stress pathways affecting neurodevelopment.

External therapies such as *Nirgundiya* Oil (derived primarily from *Vitex negundo*) and *Maha Narayana* Oil (which includes *Withania somnifera*, *Sida cordifolia*, *Rubia cordifolia*, and other *Vatha*-balancing herbs) are traditionally used in Siddha for *Abhyanga* and *Thokkanam* to pacify aggravated *Vatham* and improve muscle tone. *Vitex negundo* has been shown to exert anti-inflammatory and circulation-enhancing effects (Singh & Singh, 2010), and *Sida cordifolia* possesses anti-inflammatory and neuromuscular support actions (Venkatesh et al., 2011). Besides pharmacological effects, the tactile stimulation and improved peripheral blood flow produced by regular oil massage may enhance proprioceptive feedback and muscle activation, a concept congruent with Siddha's emphasis on physical therapies to support neuromuscular integration.

Collectively, these herbs act through multiple mechanisms - antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, neurotransmitter modulation, circulation enhancement, and transdermal stimulation - which align with *Siddha* principles of restoring *Vatham* balance and supporting neurodevelopment. These pharmacological actions provide a plausible therapeutic rationale for the observed clinical improvements in motor responsiveness, attention, and functional activity in the child managed with Siddha therapeutic protocols.

This case report demonstrates the potential effectiveness of Siddha therapeutic management in addressing motor developmental delay in a child with repaired Encephalomyelocele. Although the child had delayed attainment of developmental milestones since infancy, the primary clinical concern at presentation was the inability to walk independently despite clear speech and basic functional abilities.

Following a structured regimen of Siddha internal medicines and external therapies aimed at pacifying deranged *Vatham* and strengthening neuromuscular function, the child achieved independent walking without support. This milestone represents a meaningful functional improvement and directly addressed the chief complaint of the caregivers.

From the *Siddha* perspective, the clinical features correspond to *Balar Vatham*, and the observed progress supports the therapeutic rationale of *Vatha*-pacifying and *Rasayana*-based interventions in pediatric neurological conditions. While the outcome in this case is encouraging, further systematic clinical studies with standardized outcome measures are essential to validate the role of *Siddha* medicine in the management of neurodevelopmental delay associated with congenital central nervous system anomalies.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the potential role of *Siddha* therapeutic management in facilitating motor milestone attainment in a child with developmental delay secondary to repaired Encephalomyelocele. Despite delayed developmental progression since infancy, the child achieved independent walking without support following structured *Vatha*-pacifying and neuromuscular-strengthening interventions. The observed functional improvement supports the *Siddha* concept of *Balar Vatham* and its targeted management. Further well-designed clinical studies are warranted to substantiate these findings and establish standardized treatment protocols.

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